

Part I-Condensation of Benzaldehyde with Hippuric Acid

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Plochl¹ reported the condensation of hippuric acid with benzaldehyde and obtained 80% yield of the anhydride of α -benzylimino cinnamic acid (m. p. 164°) to which was assigned azridine structure (Ib) :

By using a mixture of acetic anhydride and sodium acetate (catalyst), Erlenmeyer² obtained 68% of benzylidene hippuric acid azlactone (m. p. 166°) which has been confirmed by the present authors.

On repeating Plochl's experiment¹ (using acetic anhydride alone as catalyst) we have now obtained 80.0% of the product in 6 hr. on water bath. The azridine structure (Ib) assigned to this product earlier was based on its reported hydrolytic to phenylglycidic acid (m. p. 155°). However, an authentic 3 sample of phenylglycidic acid has now been reported to melt at 83—84°. Also, azridines decomposes quickly in the presence of acetic acid even at a low temperature^{4,5}. Structure (Ib) thus seems erroneous.

On hydrolysing the original condensation product, (anhydride of α -benzamide cinnamic acid) with glacial acetic acid the authors obtained white crystals of α -benzamide cinnamic acid (m. p. 225°), which (as well as the anhydride itself) on further hydrolysis with conc. hydrochloric acid or caustic soda gave phenyl pyruvic acid (m. p. 157°), which was found identical with that obtained by Wislicenus⁶ by the hydrolysis of α -cyanophenyl-

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2. Erlenmeyer, E. (Jr.), *Ann.*, 1893, 275, 1.
3. Dickmann, W., *Ber.*, 1910, 43, 1035.
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5. Jones, G. D *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1944, 9, 1500.
6. Wislicenus, W., *Ber.*, 1867, 20, 592.

pyruvic acid with sulphuric acid, as well as with the one obtained by Herbst and Shemin⁷ from α -acetamido cinnamic acid. The phenylpyruvic acid prepared by the authors was confirmed through its oxime and semicarbazone. The oxime melted at 174° which agrees with the one prepared by Erlenmeyer⁸ by a different method. The semicarbazone melted at 180° (lit. 180°).

Phenylpyruvic acid may be formed in the following manner (c.f. ref.⁹).—

Pyridine, piperidine, triethylamine alone as well as in mixture failed to induce condensation.

EXPERIMENTAL

α -Benzamidocinnamic acid anhydride (Ia).—Benzaldehyde (0.53 g.), hippuric acid (0.80 g.) and acetic anhydride (1.53 g.) were heated on a water bath for 6 hr. After leaving overnight a solid product was obtained, which was boiled with water to remove hippuric acid and then filtered. Unused hippuric acid was recovered from the filtrate and the unreacted aldehyde was removed from the solid residue by washing with ether. After recrystallisation from benzene, pure substance m.p. 165° (yield, 80.9%) was obtained.

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